

MICRO-MECHANICAL RESPONSE OF A NANO-PHASED FOAM COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: SIEM (Interferometry with Electron Microscopy) is a unique experimental micro/nano mechanics technique that is capable of measuring full field strain distribution at different length scales. In this study, it is employed to investigate the micromechanics response of nano-phased foam composites made of polyurethane mixed with 1% TiO₂ nano-particles. Stress-strain relationships of the nano-phased foam composite at various length scales were obtained. It is found that the mechanical response of the material depends on the size of the specimen. Furthermore we investigated the micromechanical response of the nano-phased foam beam with a single edge crack under a three-point bending load. The displacement fields at the crack tip were obtained by SIEM.

KEYWORDS: foam, nano-particles, speckle technique, scanning electron microscope, speckle interferometry with electron microscopy.

INTRODUCTION

Polymer foam materials have been used as the core material for sandwich plates and shells. The resulting sandwich structures have gained substantial importance in marine, aerospace and ground transportation applications because of their low weight, high stiffness and high strength. When a small portion of nano-particle is added into the foam material, the stiffness of the foam material is significantly enhanced. Furthermore, the nano-phased foam tends to increase structural strength, improve insulation quality and retard fire. The superior strength of the material will enable new structural design possibilities. However, foam composite is highly heterogeneous. Most mechanical measurements are performed with strain gages which give results averaged over many foam cells. While there are microscopic observations [1-2], they are essentially limited to qualitative observations. Detailed interaction between and among cells cannot be determined. In this study we introduce a micro/nano-mechanics technique called SIEM, whereby the micromechanics responses of nano-phased foam composite made of polyurethane mixed with 1% TiO₂ nano-particles are investigated.

THE SIEM TECHNIQUE

The SIEM (Speckle Interferometry with Electron Microscopy) is an extension of the white light speckle method of strain analysis developed by Chiang and Asundi [3-4]. By using nanosized random speckles, in conjunction with a SEM (Scanning Electron Microscope) and a special algorithm called CASI [5-6], Chiang et al has extended the speckle technique to a spatial domain beyond the reach of optical microscope [7]. The essence of SIEM is as follows.

A pattern of nano-sized random particles (called speckles) is first deposited onto the surface of the specimen which is placed inside the chamber and loaded in situ. Two speckle patterns, one before and one after deformation of the specimen are recorded digitally. They are first segmented into small subimages within which the displacements of all points are assumed to be the same. The size of the subimage is chosen by the user based on the nature of problem at hand. The corresponding subimages are “compared” to yield displacement vectors using a special algorithm called CASI (Computer Aided Speckle Interferometry). Figure 1 illustrates schematically the essence of CASI.

Figure 1 Schematic of CASI for calculating displacement vectors

In Figure 1, $h_1(x,y)$ and $h_2(x,y)$ are the complex amplitudes of the light disturbance of a generic speckle subimages, before and after deformation, respectively, and

$$h_2(x, y) = h_1[x - u(x, y), y - v(x, y)] \quad (1)$$

where u and v are the displacement components along the x and y directions, respectively. First a FFT is applied to both h_1 and h_2 ,

$$\begin{aligned} H_1(f_x, f_y) &= \mathfrak{F}\{h_1(x, y)\} \\ H_2(f_x, f_y) &= \mathfrak{F}\{h_2(x, y)\} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Then, a numerical “interference” between the two speckle patterns is performed on the spectral domain, i.e.,

$$F(f_x, f_y) = \frac{H_1(f_x, f_y)H_2^*(f_x, f_y)}{|H_1(f_x, f_y)H_2(f_x, f_y)|} = \exp\{j[\phi_1(f_x, f_y) - \phi_2(f_x, f_y)]\} \quad (3)$$

where $\phi_1(f_x, f_y)$ and $\phi_2(f_x, f_y)$ are the phases of $H_1(f_x, f_y)$ and $H_2(f_x, f_y)$, respectively. Finally, a second FFT is performed to yield a halo function $G(\xi, \eta)$, i.e.,

$$G(\xi, \eta) = \mathfrak{F}\{F(f_x, f_y)\} = \overline{G}(\xi - u, \eta - v) \quad (4)$$

which is an expanded impulse function located at (u, v) . Thus, by detecting the crest of this impulse function, the displacement vector represented by the cluster of speckles within the subimage is uniquely determined. Strains are then determined using the definitions of Eulerian strain in finite deformations, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{xx} &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right)^2 \right] \\ \varepsilon_{xy} &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

It can be seen that if the derivatives are small, these strains reduce to the same expressions for the infinitesimal strains.

RESPONSE OF NANOPHASED FOAM COMPOSITE AT MACRO/MICROSCALE

We have applied the SIEM technique to investigating the mechanical response of the nano-phased foam composite at various length scales. Figure 2 shows two types of specimens that were used. The larger one is 80mm×16mm×8mm in cross-section whereas the smaller one is 25mm×4.8mm×3.6 mm in cross-section. The larger specimens were tested using a tabletop Instron uniaxial testing machine whereas the smaller ones were tested inside a SEM (Scanning Electron Microscope) at 30x magnification.

Figure 2 Dimensions of the Large and Small Specimens

Figure 3 shows the testing results. As can be seen the material is highly non-linear and the stress-strain curve is size dependent. The larger specimen shows a higher stiffness. This may be attributed to the fact that the material is porous consisting of interconnected foam cells. When the specimen is large enough the mutual constrains of the cells give rise to the stiffness of the foam. When the specimen size is reduced, the ratio of cell size to the specimen cross-

section is increased. The material effectively becomes more “porous”, hence the reduced stiffness.

Figure 3 Stress-Strain Curves of Specimens

Furthermore we investigated the micromechanical response of a nano-foam beam with a single edge crack under a three-point bending load. A specimen of 31mm×15mm×6mm was cut from a large sheet. A crack of 2.7mm was cut at the mid-point and the specimen was loaded by three-point bending inside an SEM. Silicon particles of about 1 μ m in size were spread onto the specimen surface as speckles. A typical (u,v) pair of displacement contours surrounding the crack tip at 100x magnification is shown in Figure 4. It is seen that the deformation pattern bears little resemblance to the classical crack tip displacement pattern. In addition to highly stress region near the crack tip, the interfacial region surrounding a cell is also highly stressed.

Figure 4 u and v displacement contours (contour constant = 1 μ m) depicting the deformation field of a single edge cracked foam beam under three-point bending.

CONCLUSIONS

A nano-phased foam composite made of polyurethane mixed with 1% TiO₂ nano-particles were investigated by SIEM. It is found that the mechanical properties of the material depend on the size of the specimen. The larger specimen has higher stiffness. In addition, the displacement fields were obtained at the front of crack tip in an area of 1mm×0.8mm. The deformation pattern highly depends on the size and shape of the cell.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to thank Dr. Yapa D. S. Rajapakse, Solid Mechanics Program Manager of the Office of Naval Research for support of this project under grant #N000140410357 and Dr. Hassan Mahfuz of Tuskegee University for providing us with the foam material.

REFERENCES

1. Gibson L.J., Ashby M.F., Schajer G.S., Robertsson C.I., "The Mechanics of Two-Dimensional Cellular Materials", *Proceedings of Royal Society A*, Vol. 382, 1982, pp. 25-42.
2. Gibson L.J., Ashby M.F., "The Mechanics of Three-Dimensional Cellular Materials", *Proceedings of Royal Society A*, Vol. 382, 1982, pp.43-59.
3. Chiang, F.P. and Asundi, A. "White Light Speckles Method of Experimental Strain Analysis", *Applied Optics*, Vol. 18, No. 4, 1979, pp. 409-411.
4. Asundi, A. and Chiang, F.P. "Theory and Application of White Light Speckle Methods", *Applied Optics*, Vol. 21, No. 4, 1982, pp. 570-580.
5. Chen, D.J. and Chiang, F.P., "Computer Aided Speckle Interferometry Using Spectral Amplitude Fringes", *Applied Optics*, Vol. 3, No. 2, 1993, pp. 225-236.
6. Chen, D.J., Chiang, F.P., Tan, Y.S. & Don, H.S., "Digital Speckle Displacement Measurement Using a Complex Spectrum Method" *Applied Optics*, Vol. 32, No. 11, 1993, pp. 1839-1849.
7. Chiang, F.P., Wang, Q. and Lehman, F., "New Developments in Full Field Strain Measurements Using Speckles", *Nontraditional Methods of Sensing Stress, Strain and Damage in Materials and Structures, ASTM STP 1318*, George F. Lucas and David A. Stubbs, Eds., American Society for Testing and Materials, 1997, pp. 156-169.